

A Study of Management of Diaphyseal Fractures of Tibia by Closed, Reamed Interlocking NailSubodh Kumar¹, Vikas Kumar², Narendra Kumar Sinha³^{1,2}Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, BMIMS, Pawapuri³Associate Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, BMIMS, Pawapuri

Received: 25-06-2023 / Revised: 30-07-2023 / Accepted: 22-08-2023

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background and Objectives: Many patients come to Department of Orthopaedics with tibial fractures. It is one of the common injuries occurring in adult age group. Though fracture unites with conservative treatment but associated with high morbidity. So fractures stabilization with intramedullary interlocking nail is useful to prevent morbidity. We aim to study efficacy of intramedullary interlocking nail in the treatment of closed tibial fractures.

Methods: A total of 30 patients with closed tibial fractures underwent surgery for the fracture fixation with intramedullary interlocking nail in the Department of Orthopaedics, BMIMS Pawapuri. Study duration of Two Years. Patients were selected irrespective of sex.

Results: Excellent results were obtained in 76.7% of cases, good results in 16.7%, fair in 10%. Complications include 6.7% of superficial infection, 6.7% of Anterior Knee pain.

Conclusion: Intramedullary interlocking nail is the reliable, versatile and effective treatment for closed tibial fractures. The advantage of rapid rehabilitation and relatively few complications serves to recommend this procedure.

Keywords: Intramedullary Interlocking Nail, Rehabilitation, Complications.

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Introduction

Fracture shaft of tibia is one of the common fractures encountered by the orthopaedic surgeons in their daily practice, this is because the bone is subcutaneous with less protection from the surrounding muscle. Over the years various modalities of treatment has been used. Now a days the well laid principle of biological osseous synthesis rightly applied in long bone fracture healing and hence the selection of closed intra- medullary interlocking nailing in this study.

Both operative and non-operative treatments of tibial shaft fractures have been strongly advocated. less severe fractures gradually do well without surgery, the more severe fractures requires surgery. Closed interlocking nailing helps in faster healing of fractures, because the fracture haematoma is not disturbed and also the periosteal callus formation is not disturbed. Now with better operative technique and with availability of the image intensifier interlocking nailing became the accepted mode of treatment for closed diaphyseal fractures of tibia and majority of open fracture.

Interlocking intramedullary nailing of the tibia greatly improves rotational stability and can be used for axially unstable fractures located from 7cm

below the knee joint to 4cm above the ankle joint¹. Intramedullary nails with interlocking capabilities were developed in an effort to provide a more stable fracture construct and to expand the spectrum of fractures that could be nailed while avoiding the complications of malunion^[2].

Objectives

- To maintain limb length and prevent shortening
- To study fracture healing and the union rate with intermedullary interlocking nailing.
- To prevent angulation and deformity.
- To evaluate the functional outcome and to compare with other worker study series

Materials and methods

All confirmed cases of fracture shaft of tibia in Department of Orthopedics of BMIMS Pawapuri, Bihar, Study duration of Two Years. was taken up for the study. 30 cases including both males & females were studied. Cases were also followed up at an interval of 6 weeks, 3 months and 6 months which extended. Incidence rate of fracture shaft of tibia due to RTA is 37.5% (Rockwood Greens Fractures in adults 5th edition. Vol 2) at a permissible error 35%. Size of sample works out to

be 30 using statistical formula $n=4pq/12$.

Inclusion criteria

- Patient who has been diagnosed as fracture shaft of tibia.
- Age group of more than 20 years of either sex.
- Patient who are fit for surgery.

Exclusion criteria

- Skeletally immature individual.
- Gustilo – Anderson classification of open fractures of shaft of tibia Type III.
- Neurovascular injury
- Pathological fracture.
- Nonunion

Segmental fracture: Patients were selected on the basis of History, clinical examination and radiography. X – Ray of full length of tibia- antero-posterior and lateral view was taken. All fractures were classified as per Orthopedic Trauma Association (OTA) AO classification of tibial diaphyseal fractures & these were treated with intramedullary interlocking nail. Follow up and assessment were performed using JOHNER AND WRUTH<S CRITERIA.

Preoperative preparation of patients

- Patients were kept NBM for 8-10 hours before surgery.
- IV fluids as per the need were given.
- Adequate amount of compatible blood if needed was arranged.
- Preparation of whole extremity, private parts and back was done.

Preoperatively the length of the nail is calculated by

subtracting 3 to 4cm from measurement taken from the knee joint line to tip of the medial malleolus clinically and medullary canal is measured at the isthmus on X-rays. Accordingly, a stock of interlocking nails 2cm above and below the measured length and 1mm above and below the required diameter were always kept. We have used cannulated tibial nails in our cases. Patients were operated under spinal / general anaesthesia. Patient was placed in supine position over a radiolucent operating table. The injured leg was positioned freely, with knee flexed 90° over the edge of operating table to relax the gastro-soleus muscle and allow traction by gravity.

Postoperative Care:

Immediate:

- NBM 4-6 hours postoperatively
- IV fluids/ blood transfusion if necessary
- IV antibiotics: In most of the patient's injection cefotaxime and injection gentamycin were used for 5 days followed by oral antibiotics.

IM analgesics: Patient was allowed non-weight bearing with crutch walking / walker on next postoperative day according to the general condition and tolerance of patient. Skin sutures / staples were removed on 10th - 12th postoperative day.

Depending upon the culture report and wound condition antibiotics were stopped/continued. Partial weight bearing with crutch walking /walker commenced after 10 days, depending upon the type of fracture, rigidity of the fixation and associated injuries.

Figure 1: Nail been inserted Nail positon confirmed in c-arm

Figure 2: Closure of Wound

Results: 30 patients with fracture shaft of tibia were treated with closed interlocking nailing.

Table 1: Age wise Incidence:

Age	No. of patients	Incidence
20-30	17	56.67%
31-40	8	26.66%
41-50	5	16.67%

56.67% of the patients in our study were between the age group of 20-30 years. 26.67% between 31-40 years & 16.67% between 41-50 years.

Table 2: Gender Incidence:

Sex Incidence	No Of Patient	Incidence
Male	24	80.00%
Female	6	20.00%

80.00% of the tibial fractures were seen in males & 20.00% in females, depicting male preponderance.

Table 3: Mode of injury

Table No: Mode of injury	No. of patients	Incidence
Road traffic accident	19	63.33%
Fall from height	8	26.66%
Assault	1	3.33%
Direct blow (fall of object)	2	6.66%
Total	30	100

Road traffic accidents were the most common mode of injury in our study, causing tibial shaft fractures in 19 patients which accounted for 63.33% of tibial fractures.

Table 4: Based on the involvement of Limb

Involved limb	No. of patients	Incidence
Right	21	70.00%
Left	09	30.00%
Both	0	0
Total	30	100

In this study the right tibia was affected in 70.00 % of all patients and the left tibia in 30.00% of all patients

Table 5: Type of Fracture

Type of fracture	No. of patients	Incidence
Spiral	7	23.33%
Oblique	12	40.00%
Transverse	7	23.33%
Wedge (Butterfly)	3	10.00%
communitted	1	3.33%
Total	30	100

In this oblique fractures were seen in 40.00% of patients, followed by transverse fractures (23.33%), spiral fracture (23.33%), wedge fractures (10.0%) & comminuted fracture (3.33%). No case of segmental fracture was observed.

Table 6: OTA Classification

OTA (AO) classification	No. of patients	Incidence
Type A	26	86.66%
Type B	03	10.00%
Type C	01	3.33%
Total	30	100

Table 7: Fracture Union

Fracture Union in Weeks	No. of Patient	Incidence
12-16	12	40.00%
17-20	6	53.33%
21-24	2	6.66%
TOTAL	30	100

In our study, fracture union of 16 patients (53.33%) was between 17-20 weeks & 12 patients (40.00%) between 12-16 weeks, depicting that majority of the tibial fractures united before 20 weeks.

Table 8: Complication

Complication	No. of patient	Incidence
Superficial Infection	2	6.66%
Proximal screw breakage	0	0
Distal screw breakage	0	0
Anterior knee pain	2	6.66%
shortening	0	0
Nonunion and nail breakage	0	0
Malunion	0	0

Table 9: Functional outcome

Functional outcome	No. of patients	Incidence
Excellent	23	76.66%
Good	05	16.66%
Fair	2	10.00%
Total	30	100

The functional outcome was observed to be excellent in 23 patients (76.66%), good in 5 patients (16.66%) & fair in 2 patients (10.00%).

Pre-op

Immediate post op

At 16 week

Pre op at 6 week

Immediate post op At 20 week

Discussion

Fracture shaft of tibia is one of the most common fractures encountered by the orthopedic surgeon. Over the years, various modalities of treatment have been used. The principle of biological osteosynthesis is rightly applied in long bone fracture healing and hence the selection of closed intra-medullary interlocking nailing in this study. Arne Ekeland et al [3] (1988), in study series of 45 patients noted the average age of patients to be 35 years. Similar studies by Court Brown et al [4] (1990) noted the average age to be 32.4 years & Court Brown et al [5] (1995) was 37 years. However, in our study, 56.63% of the patients were in the age group of 21-30 years and the average age being 30.8 years. Tibial shaft diaphyseal fractures were seen in the younger age group probably because they are the people who are physically active, were engaged in increased various outdoor activities and as a result most of the injuries sustained were high-velocity injuries.

A study by Hooper et al [6] (1991) showed that the incidence of fracture had male preponderance (82%). Similarly, Court Brown et al [4] (1990) & Gaston et al [7] (1999), showed the incidence among males was 81.3% & 81%, respectively. In our study, incidence in male was 80% in concordance to the other studies, pointing to the fact that incidence in male is higher probably because of their more outdoor activities, while women majorly confined themselves to the domestic activities. Court Brown et al [5] (1995), showed that the commonest mode of injury was Road Traffic Accident accounting for an incidence of 37.5%. Lawrence B. Bone et al [8] (1986), reported in an earlier series a 90% incidence of Road Traffic Accidents in tibial shaft fractures while reported a 59% incidence in his series. In our series, we have

found that 19 patients of the tibial diaphyseal fractures occurred due to road traffic accidents which accounted for an incidence of 63.33%.

In the majority of cases, they involved the patients who were the motorists, while the remaining patients tended to be pedestrians. This could be attributed to the poor road traffic sense and poor quality of roads, leading to a higher incidence of road traffic accidents in our country. In our series Type A fractures were the most commonest, they constituted 26 (86.66%). Type A fractures are unifocal fractures and in our series the incidence is higher to the series of Court Brown et al (1995), who found that Type A accounted for 54% of all tibial fractures. Our series had a higher incidence of oblique fractures in 40.00% of cases, transverse fractures made up 23.33% cases and spiral fracture (23.33%), which was comparable to a study by Sankarsan Patro et al [9] (1998), in whose series, there were 59% of these fractures. Court Brown et al reported 37.2% and Arne Ekeland [3] (1988), reported 42% of transverse and oblique fractures. The Tschern type of closed fracture in our series has been classified using the radiological criteria and in our series Tschern C1 fracture made up of 53.33% of closed fractures 16 patients. This is comparable to Tschern C1 fracture of about 53% in the series by Court Brown et al (1995). C1 type of closed fractures is commonly seen in road traffic accidents. Fracture Union was considered when patient was full weight bearing without pain; fracture site was not tender on palpation and radiograph showed osseous union. In our series, majority of fractures united within 20 weeks (24 patients).

The average time of union was 17.36 weeks. This is comparable to Anglen J.O. et al [10] (1995), where 22.5 weeks was the average union time in

a reamed nailing. Lawrence B. Bone et al (1986), reported average union time at 19 weeks. Court Brown et al (1990), reported average union time at 16.7 weeks. Arne Ekeland et al (1988), reported average union time at 16 weeks. Final assessment in our series was done at 6 months using the Johner and Wruh's criteria, taking into account of the following criteria, gait, pain, deformity, range of motion of knee, ankle and subtalar joints, shortening and Neurovascular disturbances, ability to do strenuous activities, radiological union and presence or absence of non-union. Functional outcome was graded into Excellent, Good, Fair and poor. In our series, 76.66% (23 patients) have got excellent, 16.66% (5 patients) have good, 6.66% (2 patients) have fair. Klemmet al (1986), reported 62.50% excellent, 31.8% good, 4.5% fair and 1.2% poor results. Arne Ekeland et al (1988), reported 64.4% excellent, 28.8% good and 4.4% as fair.

Conclusion

Tibial diaphyseal fractures are commonly seen in physically active young male and are commonly seen as result of road traffic accidents. The interlocking nailing restores length, Alignment and controls rotation, preserves periosteal blood supply, some amount of endosteal blood supply and with biological osteosynthesis, lowers the rate of infection and malunion. The advantage of locking screws over the conventional methods reduces the rate of malunion, loss of alignment, angulation and shortening which are commonly found in a plaster cast or functional brace. The addition of locking screws extends its indications to within 5 cm of ankle and knee joint.

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